

Schrodinger Equation Embedded Within No Source Maxwell's Equations?

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In (1), it is suggested that a Schrodinger equation $H W = E W$ is embedded in the Maxwell electromagnetic formalism for a no-source or current (i.e. photon) solution. The traditional approach is to create two wave equations (second order differential equations) from Maxwell's equations for photons (no charge sources or currents). The second order differential formally arises by removing B from a first order differential equation. This requires acting on the differential equation with an operator, making it a second order differential equation. It is well-known that the solution of the wave-equation (second order differential equation) may mathematically be written as a solution of a first order differential equation in d/dt and d/x (one dimension). We show that such a first order differential equation follows immediately from Maxwell's equations and it is this first order equation which the authors of (1) call a Schrodinger equation embedded in Maxwell's equations.

Maxwell's Equations for a Photon

A photon solution appears in Maxwell's electromagnetic equations if one removes the source charges and currents. In such a case, one obtains a wave-equation (i.e. second order differential equation) for the electric and magnetic fields.

Maxwell's equations without sources are (1):

$$\text{Grad dot } E = 0 \quad \text{grad dot } B = 0 \quad \text{grad } x E = -dB/dt \quad \text{grad } x B = 1/cc \text{ d}E/dt \text{ partial} \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Using } \text{grad } x E \rightarrow e_{ijk} d/dx_j E_k \text{ and } e_{lni} e_{ijk} = \delta(lj) \delta(nk) - \delta(l,k) \delta(n,j) \quad ((2))$$

Here e_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol.

$$1/cc \text{ d/dt d/dt partial} - \text{grad dot grad } E = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 1/cc \text{ d/dt d/dt partial } B - \text{grad dot grad } B = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Math solutions of ((3)) are $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ or $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ (or \sin) ((4)) in one dimension.

Even though (1) uses a k vector with three non-zero co-ordinates, one may always arrange the co-ordinates so that the k vector points in one direction (say the z direction) for simplicity.

The point we make is that the solutions for E and B (i.e. ((4))) are also solutions of linear equations:

$$(1/c) \text{ id/dt partial } \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) = -id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) \quad ((5a)) \text{ or}$$

$$1/c \text{ d/dt partial } \cos(-\omega t + kx) = -d/dx \text{ partial } \cos(-\omega t + kx) \quad ((5a))$$

In (1), a Fourier series expansion is used using $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and so the formalism of ((5a)) with the complex “i” appearing is used.

As a result, even though the Maxwell equations formally yield a second order differential equation ((3)), called a traditional wave equation, the solutions also satisfy a first order differential equation.

We argue that this completely analogous to the special relativistic equation:

$$EE = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4 \rightarrow EE = p^2 c^2 \text{ for } m=0 \text{ or } E=pc \quad ((6))$$

In the special relativistic case, one has both a quadratic and linear form, with the linear form $E=pc$ being most commonly used.

What (1) does is formally show that a linear differential equation of the form ((5a)) can be derived from Maxwell's equations instead of using the usual second order differential equation (wave-equation) ((3)). Given that the solution of the second order differential equation is also a solution of a first order differential equation, one may argue that a first order differential equation describes the result/solution of Maxwell's solutions together with $k \cdot E = 0$. This seems to essentially be the argument of (1), i.e.

$\nabla \cdot W = i \frac{dW}{dt}$ partial and $k \cdot W = 0$ where W is a vector function proportional to E the electric field.

We note that $k \cdot E$ or $k \cdot W = 0$ is well-known from Maxwell's equations for a photon. In particular, the Poynting vector is:

$$\frac{1}{\mu_0} E \times B = \text{direction of momentum density proportional to the } k \text{ vector} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, the k vector is perpendicular to both E and B .

As argued above, given that the solution $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is a solution of the second order differential equation as well as a first order differential equation, one may simply argue that one may describe the photon result using a first order differential equation (as it yields the same answer).

To see, however, a linear differential equation emerge from Maxwell's equations which describes E (the electric field), one may set $c=1$ and consider an E_x and B_y as existing (which are perpendicular to each other) and the direction of motion. Then: $\text{grad} \times B = dE/dt$ implies that:

$$-\frac{d}{dz} \text{partial } B_y = \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } E_x \quad ((8)) \quad (\text{Also } dB_y/dx = 0) \quad \text{Thus } B_y(z,y,t)$$

Using $\text{grad} \cdot B = 0 \rightarrow dB_y/dy = 0$ so $B_y(z,t)$ alone. Thus, $E_x(z,t)$ and $B_y(z,t)$

Given the symmetry of the differential equations with $c=1$, E magnitude = B magnitude, but this means B_y function = E_x function for all z points, so one immediately has a linear differential equation:

$$-d/dz \text{ partial } Ex(z,t) = d/dt \text{ partial } Ex(z,t) \quad ((9))$$

Any function of $-wt+kz$ satisfies ((9)). The point is that there is uniformity in space along z and so one cannot have a continuously rising or falling function. This suggests a periodic function. If one wishes to complex math to describe such periodicity, then:

$$i d/dz \text{ partial } \exp(-iwt+ikz) = i d/dt \text{ partial } \exp(-iwt+ikz) \quad ((10))$$

We argue that this is the “Schrodinger equation” of (1). In other words, it simply means that one may write a linear differential equation in d/dt (as well as d/dz) for a photon, but this follows directly from Maxwell’s equations using Ex and By as being perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion, which is often the chosen solution even for the wave-equation (second order differential equations) which also follow from Maxwell’s equations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is known from special relativity $EE = pcpc + momoccc$ that for a photon ($m_0=0$), one has $EE = ppcc$ or $E=pc$. In other words, one may write either a quadratic or linear equation. A similar feature follows for the wave-equation:

$$1/cc d/dt d/dt \text{ partial } E = d/dz d/dz \text{ partial } E \quad ((11))$$

If one chooses a periodic solution $\cos(-wt+kx)$, then this is also automatically the solution of linear differential equation:

$$1/c d/dt \text{ partial } \cos(-wt+kz) = -d/dx \cos(-wt+kz) \quad ((12))$$

An equation linear in d/dt has the appearance of a Schrodinger equation because energy of a photon is proportional to k magnitude. Thus, ((12)) has the appearance of d/dt function = energy function = H function, where H is proportional to d/dx . This is the same as $E=pc$ from special relativity for a photon. It is not a coincidence that a linear equation yields the solution for the electric or magnetic field in Maxwell’s equations. Although one may formally obtain a second order differential equation in either E or B from Maxwell’s equations as we show above, this second order differential equation arises because one wishes to formally remove B from a differential equation containing E . If one notes that the Poynting vector is $1/u_0 E \times B$ and considers the symmetry of Maxwell’s equation with no sources/currents and uses $c=1$, then E and B are on the same footing. This means that one may consider a solution in which there is only By , Ex and motion in the z direction. The magnitude of By and Ex , however, must be the same, so if they are functions of z alone (as we show above), then they are in fact the same function and one does not need to create a second order differential equation in order to remove B from an equation with E . One may simply use the first order differential equation $\text{grad } \times B = d/dt \text{ partial } E (1/cc)$. Using By and Ex (as the only nonzero components) one has $-d/dz By =$

$d/dz E_x$, but if these both only depend on t and z and have the same magnitude, one may replace the functions B_y and E_x with the same function $f(z,t)$ and so one has a linear differential equation whose solution is identical to that of the second order differential equation. A first order differential equation in d/dt with the other side of the equation representing energy then has the appearance of a Schrodinger equation, as argued in (1) in a more complex manner.

References

1.Aranjo de Asende et al. Quantum Aspects of the Classical Maxwell's Equations in free space from the perspective of the correspondence principle (2025)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/76534b6dbbbd395d4d95657f95bda54a38c85ef4>